

On glucosyl thioureides : synthesis, antibacterial and antifungal studies of certain 2-*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-1,5-disubstituted-2,4-isodithiobiurets

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2-*S*-Tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-1,5-disubstituted-2,4-isodithiobiurets have been prepared by the interaction of *S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides and *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of these compounds were evaluated.

Recently we have reported a method for preparation of several *S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides¹ by the interaction of tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl bromide and aryl thiocarbamides. These aryl isothiocarbamides because of their basic nature are known to react with alkyl/aryl isothiocyanates and produce corresponding 2,4-isodithiobiurets^{2,3}. It is interesting to study the chemistry of these glucosyl aryl isothiocarbamides with special reference to their reactions with aryl isothiocyanate.

TBG = Tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl

	R		R
a	Ph	e	<i>o</i> -Cl-Ph
b	<i>o</i> -tolyl	f	<i>m</i> -Cl-Ph
c	<i>m</i> -tolyl	g	<i>p</i> -Cl-Ph
d	<i>p</i> -tolyl		

Antibacterial activity of compounds **3a-g** was evaluated against the bacteria *S. aureus*, *P. vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *E. coli* and *Salmonella* using cup-plate method^{4,5} in DMF at a concentration of 100 µg/ml using Co-Trimazine as a reference drug. Compounds **3a**, **f** and **g** exhibited good antibacterial activity. The antifungal activity of aryl isodithiobiurets were also evaluated by cup-plate method against *A. niger* and *Fusarium* in DMF at a concentration of 100 µg/ml using Gresiofulvine as a reference drug. All compounds do not exhibited antifungal activity.

Table 1. Physical data of Compounds **3a-g***

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	yield %	[α] _D ²⁹ CHCl ₃	Picrates M.p. °C
3a	187	65.98	+67.11° (<i>c</i> = 0.596%)	122d
b	147	71.66	+71.42° (<i>c</i> = 0.70%)	195d
c	98d	65.02	+106.17° (<i>c</i> = 1.03%)	113
d	140	67.26	+234.74° (<i>c</i> = 0.852%)	189
e	138	61.26	+15.72° (<i>c</i> = 0.636%)	121
f	116-117	63.45	+25.77° (<i>c</i> = 1.16%)	126
g	209	65.64	-63.45° (<i>c</i> = 0.788%)	192d

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

Experimental

All m.ps. were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Shimadzu 8201 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra on Bruker DRX 300 spectrometer and Mass spectra on a FAB Mass spectrometer.

2-*S*-Tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-1-aryl-5-*p*-tolyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**3a-g**) were synthesized by the interaction of *S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides (**1**) with *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate (**2**).

2-*S*-Tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-1-phenyl-5-*p*-tolyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (**3a**) : *S*-Tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamide (0.005 *M*) was mixed with *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate (0.005 *M*) and the mixture was refluxed in carbon tetrachloride for 3½ h. After heating solvent was distilled off and the sticky mass

obtained as a residue was triturated several times with petroleum ether. The resultant solid was crystallized from petroleum ether as yellow crystals (65%), m.p. 187° d (Found : C, 66.72; H, 4.58; N, 4.49; S, 7.40. C₄₉H₄₁O₉N₃S₂ Calcd. for : C, 66.89; H, 4.66; N, 4.77; S, 7.28%); ν_{\max} 3363 (NH), 3066 (Ar-H), 1728 (C=O), 1596 (C=N), 1269 (C-N), 1101 (C=S), 709 (C-S) and 852 cm⁻¹ (glucopyranosyl C-H deformation)^{6,8}; δ (TMS; CDCl₃) 5.8–5.5 (N-H), 8.1–6.3 (Ar-H), 2.0–1.7 (CH₃), 5.4–4.3 ppm (H, glucopyranosyl ring)^{6,8,9,10}; M⁺, 879 (12), *m/z* 730 (50), 578 (100), 474 (15), 353 (10), 335 (12), 231 (48), 154 (38), 136 (38), 105 (100)^{11,12}. When the interaction of *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate was extended to other *S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides (**1b-g**) by similar procedure, the related 2-*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-*D*-glucopyranosyl-*l*-aryl-5-*p*-tolyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**3b-g**) were isolated.

3b : ν_{\max} 3438 (NH), 3066 (Ar-H), 1728 (C=O), 1596 (C=N), 1269 (C-N), 1101 (C=S), 709 (C-S), 854 cm⁻¹ (glucopyranosyl C-H deformation); δ (TMS; CDCl₃) 5.5–5.3 (NH), 8.05–6.24 (Ar-H), 2.3–1.2 (CH₃), 5.3–4.41 ppm (H, glucopyranosyl ring); **3e** : ν_{\max} 3363 (NH), 3066 (Ar-H), 1728 (C=O), 1596 (C=N), 1271 (C-N), 1101 (C=S), 709 (C-S), 854 cm⁻¹ (glucopyranosyl ring C-H deformation); δ (TMS, CDCl₃) 5.7–4.9 (NH), 8.06–6.26 (Ar-H), 2.2–1.2 (CH₃), 5.3–4.4 ppm (H, glucopyranosyl ring).

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